

ID	participant	fragment	phrase	code	theme	note
Case study 2 - Focus group 1 - 23 October 2023						
P1, P2, P3, P4 P7, P8, P9, P10						
Class diagram - La						
1.1	P1	la linea mi sembr diagram reprodu	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		
1.2	P1	Se è tutto a mani role of the consor	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		RUOLO DEL CONSORZIO ci sono altri frammenti che seguono, come si gestisce questa indecisione. Una possibilità è scrivere che la visualizzazione del diagramma ha subito stimolato la domanda sul cambiamento di scala. Questo è legato al concetto di completezza, loro vogliono un allineamento delle rappresentazione ...
1.3	P1	la APP al momen add a link from a	more complete elements	UML completeness		
1.4	P1	collegamento tra add a link from s	more complete elements	UML completeness		
1.5	P1	questo collegam add a link from s	more complete elements	UML completeness		
1.6	P2	Quindi io la mett add a link from s	more complete elements	UML completeness		
1.7	P2	questa cosa qui add a link from a	more complete elements	UML completeness		
1.8	P2	lo stanno facend link to animal reg	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		LINK ANIMAL REGISTRY discussione su come rappresentare animal registry: manuale o automatico?
1.9	P2	il ruolo del consor central role of the	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		
1.10	P2	La tecnologia è v technology testet	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		
1.11	P1	la stiamo sviluppi technology devel	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		
1.12	P1	Quindi io terrei il not change possi	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		lasciare così
1.13	P1	il consorzio potrebbe moltiplicare q	reuse of the models	methodology		riuso del diagramma con consorzio uguale e altri casefici - il consorzio ha il suo software
1.14	P3	se si legge in questa maniera già r	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		
1.15	P3	rappresentare qu how to represent	more complete elements	understandability vs completeness		
1.16	P1	mi sento che una understandable if	you hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.17	P1	A me sembra mo very understand	very clear	UML understandability		
1.18	P1	questa cosa di ra supply chain repr	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		
1.19	P1	questa linearità d linearity of the su	consistency with body of knowle	UML completeness		
1.20	P2	[un utente che non è esperto di qui	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.21	P1	Ma gli altri Living diagrams are diff	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
1.22	P3	li faremo, noi fare diagrams creatio	procedure for co-creation	methodology		procedura creazione diagrammi ... inserire in conclusione?
1.23	P4	Facciamo diagrai diagram validatio	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
1.24	P4	il Living Lab non lo deve vedere, ci	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
1.25	P1	lavorare a livello di coordinatore	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
1.26	P1	solo con Living Lab Coordinator	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
1.27	P1	alcuni sono più ir easy for LL coord	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
1.28	P1	Mi piace molto e useful coloring	useful coloring	UML understandability		
1.29	P2	Si (confirms --> il useful coloring	useful coloring	UML understandability		
1.30	P1	le diverse relazio hard arrow interp	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.31	P1	le frecce, in ques hard arrow interp	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.32	P1	la leggenda ... tri hard arrow interp	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.33	P4	poi lì nella legger simplify use of s	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		discussione se rinunciare ad alcuni simboli per semplificare
1.34	P3	questa distinzione utility of the leger	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.35	P1	È utile, però si de use of particular	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.36	P1	si, perché tendia hard to create de	effectiveness of visual represent	methodology		
1.37	P1	fate con la con ut methodology to c	procedure for co-creation	needs methodology		
1.38	P1	è utile avere un utility of standard	effectiveness of visual represent	methodology		questione della rappresentazione della conoscenza
1.39	P1	io lo faccio così - difficult comuni	effectiveness of visual represent	methodology		
1.40	P1	io stakeholder no not understand	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.41	P1	il ricercatore o il useful for a rease	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.42	P1	potrebbe essere useful for compa	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.43	P1	i Living Lab non t useful for a LL to	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.44	P1	Una rappresenta useful to be used	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.45	P1	io la vedo molto i very useful	very useful	UML effectiveness		
1.46	P1	comparazione tri comparison betw	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.47	P1	i progetti europei EU research proj	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.48	P3	una rappresentaz utility of the stanc	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.49	P2	Si, concordo utility of the stanc	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
1.50	P1	magari è un docu limitations of reat	effectiveness of visual repres	methodology		discussion: text vs visual representation
1.51	P3	la rappresentaz effectiveness of v	effectiveness of visual repres	methodology		
1.52	P1	non tutti sono caj can be difficult fo	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		discussion: la rappresentazione visuale è più semplice per alcuni, più difficile per altri (percezione di P1)
1.53	P1	capacità a presci need capacity to	hard symbols interpretation	UML understandability		
1.54	P1	A me piacciono n appreciation of th	very useful	UML effectiveness		
1.55	P3	se uno ha fatto u need of an initial	hard symbols interpretation	methodology		discussion: challenge related to curva di apprendimento
1.56	P1	Esatto. Esatto, pe facilitate informat	useful for comparison	UML effectiveness		
Goal diagram - i*						
1.58	P2	la parte del veter goal mismatch	more complete elements	i* completeness		discussion: a partire dal goal del vet si è scelto di mettere "salute riproduttiva"
1.59	P4	in realtà lo scopo animal selection	more complete elements	i* completeness		
1.60	P1	è una delle cose support of the AP	more complete elements	i* completeness		
1.61	P2	l'animale sia. Inse missing element	more complete elements	i* completeness		
1.62	P3	questa parte fors goal or softgoal	more complete elements	i* completeness		
1.63	P2	la parte riprodutti reproductive mar	more complete elements	i* completeness		
1.64	P2	si understandable understandable		i* understandability		
1.65	P1	io ho fatto un po difficult to unders	hard symbols interpretation	i* understandability		
1.66	P1	manca la parte (add governance	more complete elements	i* completeness		discussion: add institution / animal registry (vedi anche 1.8)
1.67	P4	in relazione al go add governance	monitoring policies and intere	i* effectiveness		
1.68	P4	la palma anche (add governance	more complete elements	i* completeness		
1.69	P1	il monitoraggio di role of policy mor	monitoring policies and intere	i* effectiveness		discussion: come l'interoperabilità interessi a chi monitora (es. consorzio). This diagram supports early discussion on strategic aspects
1.70	P3	si effective immediate		i* effectiveness		
1.71	P1	secondo me and immediate for the	immediate	i* effectiveness		
Process diagram - BPMN						
1.73	P3	Si, OK, spiegato need to explain ti	consistency	BPMN understandability		
1.74	P1	A me questo piac the overlap befor	immediate advantages detect	BPMN effectiveness		
1.75	P4	E però qui rappri complete in repr	complete process represent	BPMN completeness		
1.76	P1	dal punto di vista complete in repr	complete process represent	BPMN effectiveness		
1.77	P3	c'è una coerenza coherent repre	consistency	BPMN understandability		discussione: visualizzazione separata
1.78	P1	Certo coherent repre consistency		BPMN understandability		
1.79	P2	molto carino, i co color help unders	useful coloring	BPMN understandability		
1.80	P1	questo è molto in overlapp repr	immediate advantages detect	BPMN effectiveness		

ID	participant	fragment	phrase	code	theme	note
Case study 2 - Focus group 2 - 24 October 2023						
P5, P6, P7, P8 P11, P12, P13 P14, P15, P16						
Class diagram - UML						
2.1	P1	a me sembra molto, molto efficace	very effective		effectiveness	
2.2	P1	[a me sembra] ... molto chiaro	very clear		understandability	
2.3	P1	qui io vedo le componenti tecnolog	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.4	P1	sistema cyber-fisico	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.5	P1	già così può essere sufficiente sic	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.6	P1	mettere tutte le componenti tecnol	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	posizionamento centrale della tecnologia
2.7	P1	troviamo un modo di rappresentar	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	LINK ANIMAL REGISTRY discussi soluzione: lasciare animal registry dov'è e mettere un testo sotto che specifica l'obiettivo di collegare i due
2.8	P5	in generale non c'è fuggione ALT	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.9	P5	volendo uno potrebbe fare un diag	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.10	P5	per esempio fai un clic, spariscono	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.11	P5	Allo stato attuale è vero che abbi	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.12	P1	dipende anche da quanto si incasi	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.13	P6	per mostrarlo agli utilizzatori, fargli	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.14	P6	questo diagramma deve rappreser	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.15	P1	rimuovere ogni concetto di opzioni	more complete elements		completeness vs understandability	
2.16	P1	Ci potrebbe essere anche un colle	more complete elements		UML completeness	RUOLO DEL CONSORZIO ci sono altri frammenti che seguono, come si gestisce questa indecisione. Una possibilità è scrivere che la visualizzazione del diagramma ha subito stimolato la domanda sul cambiamento di scala. Questo è legato al concetto di completezza, loro vogliono un allineamento delle rappresentazione ...
2.17	P1	[il management software, nella visi	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.18	P1	nell'ottica della interoperabilità que	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.19	P1	sicuramente la pecora è centrale p	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	Qua si sviluppa una discussione e la possibilità di fare più diagrammi
2.20	P1	il software dovrebbe anche poi vec	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.21	P1	farne un'altro in cui c'è il camp	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.22	P1	tracciabilità interne.Tracciabilità es	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	esempio della tracciabilità interno/esterno, diverse aree evidenziate
2.23	P1	come dire, un gateway che fornisc	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.24	P1	qui ci potrebbe essere il discorso il	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.25	P4	il servizio Asl perché non è conten	more complete elements		UML completeness	ruolo veterinary asl
2.26	P1	li si tratterebbe poi di capire che ti	more complete elements		UML completeness	
2.27	P1	Ecco, su questo aspetto dell'interm	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.28	P2	il principio è quello del data Space	consistency with body of knowledge		UML completeness	
2.29	P2	alla leggenda del diagramma per n	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	
2.30	P2	Perché il è la e l'allevatore praticar	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	
2.31	P5	probabilmente intende quello però	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	discussion: force the notation in favour of understandability
2.32	P1	[questo diagramma era si è si è co	very clear		understandability	
2.33	P1	molto molto utile	very effective		effectiveness	
Goal diagram - I'						
2.34	P1	secondo me è efficace	very effective		effectiveness	
2.35	P5	rispetto ai dati ora per non magari	effectiveness of visual representation	methodology		discussion: centrality of the data, from this representation to other diagrams (e.g. entity-relationship)
2.36	P6	fare una semplice tabellina in cui s	effectiveness of visual representation	methodology		
2.37	P5	è una fase, se uno ingegnerizza il	effectiveness of visual representation	methodology		
2.38	P4	generalizzare la procedura, quindi	procedure for co-creation	methodology		
2.39	P1	qui però c'è la infrastruttura, ma l'A	more complete elements		completeness	discussion: non trova app, necessità di centralizzare le tecnologia - deviazione dalla notazione e convenzione per codices
2.40	P5	dovremmo stabilir missing goal dati	more complete elements		completeness	aggiungere goal
2.41	P1	per rappresentare questa cosa io l	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	
2.42	P5	per rendere l'Information System c	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	
2.43	P4	come nel caso dell'altro diagramm	keep the representation simple		completeness vs understandability	
2.44	P5	la freccia su scan Bluetooth dovret	hard symbols interpretation		understandability	cambare nel diagramma
2.45	P4	nostra convenzione chela tecnolog	keep the representation simple		effectiveness	
Process diagram - BPMN						
2.48	P1	A me sembra molto efficace questi	very effective		effectiveness	
2.49	P1	qui l'unica cosa è che tutto il proce	high level of detail		understandability vs completeness	discussion: questione delle viste separate per migliorare la leggibilità
2.50	P4	avere una visione d'insieme divent	multiple objectives of the representa		understandability	
2.51	P4	Ah, secondo me è molto efficace E	multiple objectives of the representa		effectiveness	
2.52	P4	questo può essere utile per diciam	multiple objectives of the representa		effectiveness	
2.53	P1	queste rappresentazioni che senz	linearity		understandability	
2.54	P2	me quest'ultimo è abbastanza chi	clear		understandability	
2.55	P3	E anche per me è chiaro	clear		understandability	
2.56	P2	soprattutto vedere cosa succede d	immediate advantages detection		effectiveness	
2.57	P3	la trovo estremamente chiara	clear		understandability	
Methodology						
2.59	P3	potrebbe essere utile anche nel se	tool for analysis		effectiveness	

ID	participant	fragment	phrase	code	theme	note						
Case study 2 - Focus group 3 - 4 December 2023												
P11. P12. P13. P14. P15.												
Process diagram - BPMN												
3.1	P1	Quindi comunque sono comprensibili	hard symbols in		understandability							
3.2	P1	Quindi penso di sì, ma una volta di	hard symbols in		understandability							
3.3	P2	Quindi se riteniamo utili il diagramma	multiple objective		effectiveness							
3.4	P2	I don't pay attention to the small icons	hard symbols in		understandability							
Goal diagram - i*												
3.5	P1	allora gli obiettivi ci sono ... Senza dubbio			completeness							
3.6	P1	E anche in questo caso, se per sal	hard symbols in		understandability							
3.7	P2	L'errore nella parte del veterinario	hard symbols in		understandability	I think that animal health is a primary objective, while farm productivity is a secondary objective						
3.8	P3	more understandable with respect to	very clear		understandability							
Class diagram UML												
3.9	P3	Queste due cose qua pensate che	more complete e		completeness							

ID	code	mentioned by	theme	example
1.1	+ consistency with body of knowledge	FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG1#P3;FG2#P1	UML completeness	it seems in line with what was discussed previously (FG2#P1)
1.2	- more complete elements	FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG1#P3;FG2#P5	UML completeness	It is fundamental to add a link between the software agency, the agronomist and the vet. In fact, this relation highlights the information exchange being carried out in co-developing the mobile application, and provides the analysts with a clear indication of the actors directly involved in the design of the system
1.3	+ multi-layer representations	FG2#P5;FG2#P6	UML completeness	This can be done with layers. So we can have a very simple layer with the minimum elements, and then you can try to add new layers in case you want to understand the system's complexity, but at the same time, you want to digitalise other parts of the broader system
1.4	+ useful colouring	FG1#P1;FG1#P2	UML understandability	I was also thinking whether we can identify with different colours the digital from non-digital
1.5	- hard symbols interpretation	FG1#P1;FG1#P3;FG1#P4;FG2#P2;FG2#P5	UML understandability	what do id and coords mean?
1.6	+ useful for comparison	FG1#P1;FG1#P3;	UML effectiveness	It could be useful for every one of us to see the differences among LLS
1.8	+ reuse and adaptation	FG1#P1	UML effectiveness	The consortium could use the same diagram in different situations
1.9	- more complete elements	FG1#P3;FG1#P4;FG2#P1;FG2#P5	i' completeness	In the area of the vet there is only milk productivity and milk quality. Actually, the vet is not interested in this. Instead, the vet's goal is the animal health, from the productive and reproductive perspective
1.10	+ consistency	FG2#P1;FG2#P4;FG2#P5	i' understandability	We could deviate a bit from the standard of the notation in favour of readability
1.11	- hard symbol interpretation	FG1#P1;FG2#P5;FG3#P1	i' understandability	I think that animal health is a primary objective, while farm productivity is a secondary objective
1.13	+ monitoring policies and interactions	FG1#P1;FG1#P4	i' effectiveness	This kind of representation related to the goals helps to establish if there are potential conflicts between the actors.
1.14	+ high level of detail	FG2#P1	BPMN effectiveness	The process is seen from the perspective of the agronomist, then from the point of view of the vet, from the farmer, from the factory...they are all there, well done
1.15	+ useful colouring	FG1#P2	BPMN understandability	I really like the idea of using the colours, I think this is very intuitive
1.16	+ linearity	FG2#P1	BPMN understandability	these representations with straight lines are clean and very understandable
1.17	+ consistency	FG1#P1;FG1#P3	BPMN understandability	the single views are consistent with each other
1.18	- hard symbol interpretation	FG3#P1;FG3#P2	BPMN understandability	I don't pay attention to the small icons inside the boxes containing the actors' tasks
1.19	+ multiple objectives of the representation	FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG2#P4;	BPMN effectiveness	These representations are very effective and can support the design of the service helping to decide how to distribute tasks among actors and how to manage a service in a different scenario; for example, we could have the same process with different actors involved and a different task distribution
1.20	+ immediate advantages detected	FG1#P1;FG1#P4;FG2#P2	BPMN effectiveness	presenting the single point of view, the diagram really shows who has the costs, who has the benefits. In the end, it will emerge thanks to these diagrams
1.21	+ useful analysis tool	FG2#P3	methodology	it could be useful in different contexts as a tool for analysis
1.22	+ effectiveness of visual representation	FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG2#P3	methodology	Visual representation is a good support for memory and is more effective than reading a textual document, which is a more time-consuming activity
1.23	+ reuse of the models	FG1#P1	methodology	we can work on replicability of the models
1.24	+ procedure for co-creation of models	FG1#P2;	methodology	Will the other LLS do the diagrams on their own?

Structure diagram UML		Goal diagram i*	Process diagram BPMN	Methodology
				tool for analysis FG2#P3
<i>Completeness</i>		<i>Completeness</i>	<i>Completeness</i>	effectiveness of visual rep FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG2#P3
more complete elements	FG1#P1;FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG1#P	more complete elements	FG1#P3;FG1#P4;FG2#P1;FG2#P5	FG2#P1 reuse of the models FG1#P1
multi-layer representations	FG2#P5,FG2#P6			procedure for co-creation FG1#P2;
<i>Understandability</i>		<i>Understandability</i>	<i>Understandability</i>	
useful colouring	FG1#P1;FG1#P2	keep the representation symple	FG2#P1;FG2#P4	useful colouring FG1#P2
hard symbols interpretation	FG1#P1;FG1#P3;FG1#P4;FG2#P	hard symbols interpretation	FG1#P1;FG2#P5	linearity FG2#P1
				consistency FG1#P1;FG1#P3
				hard symbols interpretation FG2#2
<i>Effectiveness</i>		<i>Effectiveness</i>	<i>Effectiveness</i>	
useful for comparison	FG1#P1;FG1#P3;	monitoring policies and interope	FG1#P1;FG1#P4	multiple objectives of the represent FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG2#P4;
consistency with body of knowledg	FG1#P1;FG1#P2;FG1#P3;FG2#P1			immediate advantages detection FG1#P1;FG1#P4;FG2#P2
reuse and adaptation	FG1#P1			high level of detail FG2#P1